

What's in a name? Defining new entrants to farming

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Abstract

New entrants to farming are eligible for targeted supports through the CAP. The intention of new entrant supports is to promote innovativeness and sustainability in the agricultural sector through generational renewal. However, new entrants, be they successors or fully new into the industry, still face several barriers over and above other longstanding farmers, including lack of access to necessary capital, land and housing. There is also ambiguity about the success of the new entrant supports in achieving their stated objectives. In this article, we draw on results from an online survey distributed to new entrants and those working in new entrant facing support services across Europe. As part of this survey respondents were asked to record how they would define a 'new entrant farmer'. Respondents identified three key areas where new entrants could be better defined: experience in farming, age limits, and the innovativeness of business practices. We argue that the definition of new entrant utilised in policy supports could be more specifically targeted towards their objectives, distinguishing supports for generational renewal from those from innovation and sustainability. Such reframing could help to encourage more climate-friendly farming and the production of additional public goods from agriculture.

Keywords

New entrant farmers; defining new entrants; innovation; Europe

Introduction

New entrants are acknowledged as important to increasing the levels of innovation, business sustainability and environmental protection on EU farms (Regidor 2012). The perceived shortage of new entrants is recognised as the 'new entrant problem': Europe's farmers are ageing, although there is considerable variation between member states (see Coopmans et al., 2021; Zagata et al 2017). Although traditionally, succession through family ties has been the most common means

through which to start a farm business across Europe (Jack et al., 2019), there is a growing trend toward new entrant farmers who do not have family ties to farming, or even a longstanding background in farming. These newcomers instead bring skills and experience from a diverse range of previous careers (Pindado et al., 2018).

In recognition of the importance of facilitating newcomers and generational succession, the European Commission has established several supports. These include the Young Farmer Payment, a compulsory scheme under regulation (EU) No. 1307/2013 of Pillar One which allows Member States to allocate up to 2% of the direct payments envelope to the Young Farmer Payment. In the 2023-2027 CAP, this measure is increased to a 3% minimum. Under Pillar Two, support for young farmers is comprised of Business Start-up aid for young farmers and the opportunity to introduce favourable loans and bank guarantees. New proposals for 2023-2027 also include the removal of age limits on new entrant supports (previously limited to individuals who are 40 years old or younger), and reallocation of supports to small-scale farmers, which will disproportionately benefit newcomers, owing to the typically smaller size of new entrant farms. In this paper we consider how the definition of new entrants utilised in these and prospective further supports could more suitably be targeted in order to achieve the associated objectives.

Defining New Entrants

Newcomers enter the agricultural sector through a variety of routes. Zagata et al. (2017), based on the EIP Agri Focus group on new entrants work on defining new entrants, developed the typology in Figure 1. The figure demonstrates that 'new entrants' range from direct successors – who may or may not make major changes to the farming operations, to new entrants, who have varying degrees of off-farm experience. The resources to farm may also be accessed through spouses and other family members i.e. an individual who is completely new to farming may nevertheless have a spouse or partner who was raised on a farm. New entrants are thus very difficult to distinguish in practice.

Figure 1: Flowchart highlighting the different types of new entrants (source, Zagata et al. 2017, adapted from EIP-AGRI Report, 2016)

As highlighted in an EIP-AGRI report (2016: 7), ‘the first challenge in assessing new entrants to farming is to adequately define them’. Access to subsidies requires a definition of new entrants to farming, in order to determine eligibility. The current definition of new entrants to farming is provided by Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament:

Young farmer means a person who is no more than 40 years of age at the moment of submitting the application, possesses adequate occupational skills and competence and is setting up for the first time an agricultural holding as head of that holding’ (Article 2, paragraph n).

The EU definition of new entrants thus emphasises the age, competence, and leadership of an agricultural holding. As such, it conflates new entrants with young farmers (Zagata and Sutherland 2015). However, it is difficult to accurately identify the number of new entrant farmers in Europe: Eurostat figures are organised into decades (35 – 44, 45-54 etc); that is, for statistical purposes, ‘young farmers’ are considered to be farmers under the age of 35. At present, new entrant supports (e.g., Business Start-up for young farmers in Pillar 2) also add a further criterion – specifically, being the head of the holding for less than 5 years.

In contrast, the USDA initially defined a beginning farm as ‘one operated by a farmer who has operated a farm for 10 years or less’ (Ahern and Newton, 2009); that is, the focus is on the operation of the

farm, regardless of age. The USDA use of 10 years recognises the length of time it takes for a farm to become well established. However, more recently, USDA framed new entrants as:

“A natural person, group of people or legal entity who have within the past five years established a new agricultural holding or farming business in their own name(s). The natural person, group of people or legal entity should be actively farming (i.e., producing agricultural products for sale) and be either establishing a new agricultural holding or returning to a family-held holding after a minimum of 10 years of off-farm employment.” (USDA in Sutherland et al, 2016)

The new definition emphasises the multiple ways in which a farm can be held i.e. including corporations and other legal entities, but also the production of agricultural products. The new definition also actively seeks to remove direct successors from consideration.

Figure 2: New entrant with his organic beef herd, Scotland, UK

As suggested in the EIP-AGRI report (2016), new entrants can bring several resources gained outside of farming, including skills, networks and financial capital, leading to innovative production, marketing and management practices that spread throughout farming systems. Such skills, networks and capital are currently often absent in definitions of new entrants. However, such skills should perhaps be considered more strongly when defining new entrants, given their potential to enhance the sustainability of the agricultural sector in the future (Zagata and Sutherland, 2015). Establishing an updated definition for new entrants that encompasses not only (or solely) farmer characteristics, but

also an indication of the type of farming (i.e., innovative farming focusing on sustainability through new skills and ideas) that should be undertaken, could help to focus farming on a more sustainable and future-oriented footing. This is especially key, perhaps, given the growing need for enhanced focus on farming practices and processes that simultaneously offer good quality food, a growing range of public goods from agriculture and a sustainable livelihood for those involved in the agricultural production.

Methodology

We draw on results from an online survey distributed to new entrants and those working in new entrant facing support services across Europe. As part of this survey respondents were asked to record how they would define a 'new entrant farmer'. The overall aim of this survey was to gather information on the specific issues and barriers that new entrants face, as well as the potential support mechanisms that can help to reduce some of these barriers. The survey questions were devised by researchers from the H2020 NEWBIE project (New Entrant netWork: Business models for Innovation, entrepreneurship and resilience in European agriculture). Ethical approval was obtained for the survey through the James Hutton Institute's Ethics in Social Research Board, and the survey was distributed online across the registered Newbie participants and additional farming networks by all 10 partners. The survey was open to anyone involved in farming (i.e., all farmers, advisors and academics). The survey was produced and distributed in August-September 2021, using Qualtrics (online survey software) and was distributed in the national language of the member countries. The results include both closed response questions and open-ended questions. In total, 352 completed questionnaires were collected within the survey, including 200 responses to the question of 'in two sentences or less please define what a new entrant is to you?'. These responses represented opinions of a range of farmers (with varying levels of experience) and those of professionals that support farmers (e.g., advisors, media, researchers). Responses to the questionnaire were also obtained from across all nine NEWBIE partner countries: Belgium (6), Bulgaria (11), France (33), Germany (81), Ireland (5), Netherlands (10), Portugal (17), Slovenia (20) and UK (17). The open-ended questions were translated into English by the relevant partners before being analysed using NVivo software.

Results

Overall, there was considerable variation in terms of proposed definitions, further emphasising that there is not yet common agreement on how to constitute a 'new entrant farmer'. A wide range of definitions emerged from within each country, with no clear commonalities when comparing definitions from one country to another. However, there were a number of themes which emerged:

1. the level of experience in farming;
2. the importance of innovation and new ideas for creating a sustainable future
3. whether innovative successors should be considered new entrants.

Importantly, although a few respondents identified age restrictions (e.g. under 30 or under 40 years of age), most recognised that new entrants could be of any age. Most definitions instead focussed on the level of experience or specific farming practices.

(1) Experience in farming

A popular aspect of many of the proposed definitions concerned the level of experience of the new entrant with either farming in general, or in managing the farm. This reflects the importance of distinguishing active management of the farm from more passive roles of farm successors as farm labourers. For some respondents, this was stated in concrete terms of 3, 5 or 10 years, as highlighted below. For one Irish respondent (Ireland A3), a new entrant was, 'someone who has entered a business that is agriculture based within the previous 2- 3 years' (Ireland A1). Whilst, for others, the experience limit was five years: 'People who have been active in the field of agriculture for less than 5 years, or who have made a change of farming branch/ speciality in the last 5 years and are therefore not yet fully established in their field and still have some uncertainties (Germany B12)'. Yet, for others, the experience was less tied to the number of years completed in farming and was more concerned with the experience in making business-critical decisions – to thus include certain successors as new entrants, especially if undertaking new ventures.

For instance, for one Slovenian respondent, 'new entrant status is not tied to the number of years completed. A new entrant is "new" if he runs the farm for less than 10 years. (Slovenia A5). Yet, for others, the experience is tied to the time of making business-critical decisions, rather than merely time spent farming, for illustration, a new entrant is, 'someone making business-critical decisions for the first five years or so. I.e., not gradually taking over from a parent. (UK A10). Although though this level of experience was agreed to be an important characteristic, the associated amount of time a new entrant spent at this level was less clear.

(2) The importance of bringing innovation and new skills ideas for creating a sustainable future

A popular focus of the responses was the importance of 'new entrants' to be innovative and bring new ideas to farming. Some of these ideas could help reduce the negative impacts emerging from, for

example, the climate emergency through more sustainable and innovative business practices. For example, for one Dutch respondent (Netherlands A4), 'a new farmer is the one who can break old patterns to meet the challenges of changes in society in an innovative way'. Similarly, for one Portuguese respondent (Portugal A10), a new entrant is 'a farmer who is more dedicated to managing the activity as a sustainable business, to new technologies, including communication. More aware of the market and its challenges'.

Others went one step further, emphasising that this innovation was often a result of skills brought to their business from previous non-farming careers. This is illustrated below:

'For me, newcomers to agriculture are people who think innovatively, who observe the changes brought about by politics, the media and consumer behaviour, and who want to make a targeted difference in the industry by starting afresh. They may even combine their previous non-agricultural professions with a new start, e.g., in farm education. They are courageous and willing to do something good and sustainable for their lives and those of their fellow human beings.' (Germany A3)

For this respondent, being innovative and using such innovative skills for the wider societal good, were key aspects of being a 'new entrant', rather than any specific age or experience characteristics of the farmer. This sentiment was widely echoed in the 200 definitions, including this definition from a Dutch respondent, who defined a new entrant 'as an innovative entrepreneur who starts with an agricultural business that often renews or improves the sustainability of the sector as a whole (Netherlands A8). Thus, innovation was linked to the sustainability potential of the wider agricultural sector.

Relatedly, although, perhaps not for inclusion in a definition, there were numerous references to the fact that new entrants needed to be 'brave' and 'determined' thus, recognising the increasingly difficult context and challenges which new farmers face (i.e., the need to be innovative, the need to also provide wider public good from farming, and farm in more competitive markets). Such sentiment is articulated well by one Slovenian respondent: 'A brave, penetrating, innovative and very hard-working (young) man/woman who has a special joy for working in nature and growing food' (Slovenia A8). There is recognition of the difficulties that new entrants face now, over and above difficulties that previous generations of new entrants may have faced.

Overall, innovation and the importance of new skills were frequently mentioned in the proposed definitions, and across the full range of countries from which responses were obtained. We, therefore, argue that such sentiment should be considered in an updated definition of new entrants. Innovation was also, however, possible, from certain successor farmers – not only full newcomers to farming.

(3) Innovative successors as new entrants

Study participants disagreed about whether successors should be categorised as ‘new entrants’. Successors and new entrants without family ties to farming faced different challenges. However, synergy could be made with successor new entrants only being considered ‘new entrants’ if they were establishing a new business on the farm (i.e., not merely continuing the same farming practices as their family members). For example, ‘people who are completely new to farming but also farmers who are entering new branches of the business or taking over the farm.’ (Germany D2). Similarly, for one UK respondent, a new entrant had ‘no family link to agriculture or breaking away from family enterprise’. In this case, a successor could only be a new entrant if their new business was not associated with any existing family farming business. Some respondents, took this one step further, defining a new entrant as ‘someone working in agriculture whose parents and grandparents didn't work in agriculture and who didn't inherit agricultural land.’.

Thus, for a substantial cohort of respondents, successors could only be considered new entrants if they were undertaking a new venture which was separate from the family farm. These ‘successors’ faced some different challenges to those of complete newcomers to farming in terms of the resources they could already access.

Figure 3: New entrant vegetable producers in Bulgaria

Discussion and conclusion

The findings presented demonstrate some disconnections in current new entrant support policies. First – it is widely agreed that new entrants can be of any age. Particularly owing to the time it can take to accumulate the resources to start a farm – either personally or through inheritance – there are a cohort of individuals and households which do not become farmers until they are over the age of 40. Study participants pointed to the importance of supporting individuals who are new to making major decisions on the farming enterprise. The logical supports for these individuals and households is assistance in making these decisions i.e. targeted advice, rather than grant programmes per se.

Second, study participants made the link between new entrants and levels of innovation towards more sustainable farming practices. This is also the justification provided in policies supporting new entrant schemes. We suggest that this transition towards sustainable agriculture should be the aim of all farmers, not simply those who are young and/or new to the sector. Some new entrants will necessarily not be particularly innovative or oriented towards environmental or social sustainability,

because they will prioritise establishing a financially viable farm business. To this end, we suggest that supports aimed at increasing innovation and transition towards desirable farming practices are made available to all farmers, not simply new entrants. The findings show that such a focus on innovation and sustainability is perhaps more important than a focus on defining new entrants according to time in the farming sector, farming background or farmer age

Third, study respondents identified the difference in supports needed by new entrants who have, and who have not been able to access family supports. Across Europe, new entrant supports are primarily received by farming successors (Zagata et al. 2017). We suggest that grant supports in aid of enabling newcomers to the industry should be oriented primarily towards newcomers who are not inheriting farming resources. However, we recognise that inheritance can be variable – successors may need to pay out other siblings, or allow for their parents’ retirement. We therefore suggest that supports which enable farm succession planning can be particularly effective in these situations.

Ultimately, we argue that the focus for defining new entrants should also be on the models that they are adopting and innovations they are utilising to create a more sustainable and resilient farming sector – rather than any definition based solely on age or family background irrespective of the business model that is ultimately followed.

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